

A Case of Pyometra in a 2 Year Old Yankasa Ewe

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A two year old Uda ewe was presented to the Large Animal Unit of Veterinary Teaching Hospital, Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto with complaints anorexia and the animal having progressive emaciation. The ewe was said to have been purchased about four months ago prior to presentation and that was suspected to be pregnant at the time of purchase. On clinical examination, the ewe was weak, emaciated with the rectal temperature 38.9°C, pulse rate 76 beats/minute, and respiratory rate 44 cycles/minute. Abdominal ultrasound scan (USS) of the ewe revealed pyometra which was surgically evacuated through hysterotomy.

Key words: Abdominal, Ultrasound, pyometra, hysterotomy

INTRODUCTION

Pyometra is accumulation of purulent exudate in the uterine lumen. This condition is not common in sheep and where it occurs, it is usually a complication of metritis and ovulation during anestrus period that result in persistent corpus luteum (Pugh and Baird 2012). Clinically, animals with pyometra shows abnormal estrous activity like anestrus, purulent vaginal discharge in open cervix pyometra and presence of echogenic fluid in the uterine lumen following ultrasound scan (USS). There is usually no sign of endotoxemia in sheep. In the cows, pyometra is commonly diagnosed at postpartum due to ovulation occurring before uterine clearance of bacteria takes place (Bondurant, 1999). Frajblat, 2005 reported 7.8% of pyometra in cows.

The present case described a closed cervix pyometra in a sheep that was previously known and thought to be pregnant according to history obtained from the client. This is the first time the author is experiencing the case of pyometra and most importantly diagnosed through transcutaneous abdominal ultrasound scan (USS) in sheep.

Case Presentation

A two year old Uda ewe was presented to the Large Animal Unit of Veterinary Teaching Hospital, Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto with complaints anorexia and the animal having progressive emaciation. The ewe was said to have been purchased about four months ago prior to presentation and that was suspected to be pregnant at the time of purchase. On clinical examination, the ewe was weak, emaciated with the rectal temperature 38.9°C, pulse rate 76 beats/minute, and respiratory rate 44 cycles/minute. Abdominal ultrasound scan (USS) of the ewe with 3.5 MHz 2 multi lscan revealed pyometra. There was report of routine deworming but none of vaccination.

The ewe was then stabilized and evaluated for cesarean section for the echogenic purulent exudate to be evacuated through hysterotomy.

The surgical evacuation was carried out according to the description by (Mike and Jackson 2000). The right Para lumbar fossa was liberally shaved cleaned and scrubbed with antiseptic solution. The patient was placed on dorsal recumbency and the right paralumbar fossa shaved, cleaned and scrubbed with antiseptic solution for a sterile procedure. The initial linear skin incision on the prepared site was incised through the various layers of the

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Plate 1: Sonograph of the ewe with 5.0 MHz transcutaneous probe showing pyometra

Plate 2: The ewe was placed on right lateral recumbency after the left paralumber region was liberally shaved, cleaned and scrubbed for aseptic procedure

abdomen till the abdominal cavity. The uterus was manually exteriorized, hysterotomy performed on the less vascularized part of the fluid filled uterus and the pus content evacuated. The organ was carefully packed with sterile drape to avoid spillage of the pus content into the

abdominal cavity. After reasonable evacuation, the uterine lumen was lavaged with mild antiseptic solution and two boli of vetcotrim placed in before hysterotomy closure. The peritoneum, skin muscles, the fascia were closed separately with chromic catgut size 2 in a simple

Plate 3: The pyometric uterus was exteriorized to the surgical field after opening up the skin through peritoneum for evacuation.

Plate 4: Suturing of the hysterotomy incision after evacuation and lavage of the uterus with mild antiseptic solution (clohexidine).

Plate 5: Sutured skin incision with nylon size 2 in a ford interlocking pattern

continuous pattern while the skin was closed with nylon size 2 in a ford interlocking pattern. The patient was placed on post surgical management.

DISCUSSION

The prevalence of dystocia is very low, with 1.4% reported by Ahammand *et al.*, (2015). Ultrasound diagnosis of pyometra is through the appearance of increased volume of accumulated echogenic uterine content without fetus and cotyledon, closed cervix and presence of corpus luteum (CL) on the ovary Sheldon *et al* (2008). Basic treatment protocol include the administration of PGF₂ α or a systemic analogue to stimulate uterine defense mechanism by destroying the corpus luteum which eventually lead to seasion of release of progesterone as reported by Sharma *et al* (2018). The decrease in progesterone and increase in estrogen concentrations associated with luteolysis and follicular growth result in maximal resistance of the uterus to bacterial infection. Sharma *et al* (2018).

CONCLUSION

This is the first documented case of pyometra in ewe diagnosed through medical imaging (USS) in the

Teaching Hospital. The patient was previously known to be pregnant with typical display of some features attributed with pregnancy like non return to heat, development of the udder, but the animal was presented when it could not be said to have lambed after a long period. Pyometra are known to be without systemic involvement. This is connected with the normal vital parameters obtained from the patient during clinical examination. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first pyometra diagnosed through USS in the Teaching Hospital.

RECOMMENDATION

The need for pregnancy monitoring or ante natal evaluation of pregnant sheep should be part of routine veterinary care to limit huge financial cost and management of presumed pregnant so that early non compactible anomalies with pregnancy can terminated early enough. The tendency of the animal having postpartum complication like infertility or sterility can be minimized if early medical intervention is in place.

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